

Open-Source Privileged Access Management

A Reference Architecture for Constrained Administrative Delegation in Small and Mid-Size Enterprise Environments

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Abstract

Many small and mid-size enterprises know that they need tighter control over privileged access but cannot justify the cost, staffing, or rollout complexity of a commercial Privileged Access Management (PAM) platform. This paper documents a reference deployment that used open-source components and existing virtualization infrastructure to broker administrative sessions, enforce constrained delegation through Just Enough Administration (JEA), route approvals through an existing messaging workflow, and record privileged activity for audit. The design is intended for roughly 50-500 user environments that already run Active Directory and can support basic PowerShell, Linux, and virtualization administration. In the reference deployment described here, implementation required approximately 20 architect-hours, and ongoing maintenance averaged 2-4 administrator-hours per month. These figures reflect one production deployment and should be considered illustrative rather than universal.

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1. Executive Summary

Commercial Privileged Access Management is often priced and staffed for larger organizations. For many 50-500 user environments, the practical result is either to keep standing privileged access in place or to build partial controls around tickets, spreadsheets, and trust. This paper documents a reference deployment that tried to close that gap.

The deployment used open-source components on existing virtualization infrastructure to broker sessions, gate password resets and just-in-time elevation through approval workflows, and constrain administrative actions at the PowerShell runtime boundary. It was built for an on-premises Active Directory environment and assumes that an organization can already operate basic Linux services, PowerShell remoting, and centralized logging. In the reference deployment described here, implementation required approximately 20 architect-hours across build, configuration, and tuning, and ongoing maintenance averaged 2-4 administrator-hours per month. These figures reflect one production deployment and should be treated as illustrative rather than universal.

The reference deployment was designed to reduce the following common failure modes:

- Constrained delegation with time-bounded elevation for daily administrative operations. No operator account holds persistent membership in privileged groups; elevation is explicit, time-bounded, and automatically revoked.
- Runtime-enforced privilege boundaries via Just Enough Administration (JEA). Helpdesk-tier operators can reset passwords and unlock accounts but cannot touch privileged groups, file systems or arbitrary code paths. These limits are enforced at the PowerShell runtime layer and not at the policy layer.
- Session brokering with 90-day retention of full-session recordings, proxied through a browser, so that no administrator workstation holds direct credentials to the target systems.
- Approval workflows are tied to the organization's existing messaging platform, so every privileged action produces a human-attributable audit record before execution.
- Blast radius isolation via tiered deployment, sealed administrative appliances for the execution tier, and host-based detection controls.

Reference deployment scope: This architecture was deployed in a multisite manufacturing environment and used in production in place of a commercial PAM product. It was exercised during routine administrative work and security operations, which provided practical feedback on constrained delegation boundaries, session brokering, approval flow reliability and audit logging under production conditions.

Intended audience: The deployment described here assumes an architect with working knowledge of Active Directory, PowerShell, Linux system administration, and basic virtualization or container-host operations. Organizations without this skill set in-house should factor external consulting or commercial PAM into their evaluation.

This is not a turnkey product; rather, it is a reference architecture for practitioners capable of operating it.

2. Threat Model

A PAM architecture that does not clearly state what it defends against and what it does not invites misplaced confidence. This section enumerates the threats that this design is explicitly built to mitigate, the threats it partially addresses, and the threats that remain the responsibility of other controls. The threat model is framed in the vocabulary of zero trust architecture, as defined in NIST SP 800-207 [1], with explicit trust boundaries between tiers and no implicit trust granted based on network position.

2.1 In-Scope Threats (Primary Defenses)

- Credential theft from administrator workstations. Administrators do not hold credentials to target the systems. Session brokering means that target credentials live only on the gateway, and gateway authentication is federated to the identity provider with multi-factor enforcement.
- Standing privilege lateral movement. No account holds persistent membership in privileged groups for routine operations. Elevation is explicit, time-bound, logged, and approved by a second party.
- Helpdesk account compromise. A compromised helpdesk identity cannot perform operations outside the constrained-delegation boundary. Privileged groups, the file system of the execution tier, and arbitrary PowerShell are blocked at the runtime layer, not at a policy layer.
- Insider abuse of administrative tools Every privileged action requires approval from a second person in the messaging platform before the workflow can proceed. All sessions and API calls are logged to a centralized SIEM, independent of the administrator's ability to alter local logs.
- Unauthorized privilege persistence. Time-bounded elevation uses a scheduled removal mechanism combined with a Group Policy baseline that enforces the intended membership of privileged groups. A stale JIT membership is surfaced by both the audit log and enforcement layer.

2.2 Partially-Addressed Threats

- In-VLAN adversary with traffic interception capability. Segmentation and host-based IDS reduce the likelihood of this scenario; however, the architecture assumes that an attacker already positioned on the management VLAN with packet manipulation capability has already defeated prior controls. Internal TLS uses a self-signed private certificate authority, and external traffic uses CA-signed certificates at the edge proxy.
- Identity provider compromise: If the identity provider is fully compromised, the authentication guarantees of the architecture are no longer valid. The design depends on the IdP to enforce MFA and pre-authentication. Organizations should independently harden the identity tier.
- Supply-chain compromise of open-source components. The architecture pins container images and distribution packages to known versions but does not independently verify upstream integrity. Organizations in high-threat sectors should layer reproducible builds, image signing, and software bill of materials practices.

2.3 Out-of-Scope Threats

- Physical compromise of the hypervisor. If an adversary obtains persistent physical access to the hypervisor, all guarantees of the architecture fail. Physical security is the responsibility of the facility and host-hardening controls.
- Zero-day exploitation of core infrastructure components. Unknown vulnerabilities in the virtualization platform, operating system kernel, workflow engine, or session gateway software are not independently compensated by this architecture. Timely patching and vulnerability management are essential prerequisites.
- Social engineering of the approval step. If an approver rubber-stamps every incoming request without reading it, the approval control is degraded to an audit-only control. Approver training and approval fatigue mitigation are operational responsibilities outside the architecture itself.

3. Design Principles

This architecture adapts the tiered administrative model described in Microsoft's Enterprise Access Model [2]. This model succeeds the Enhanced Security Admin Environment (ESAE) pattern [6] and scales down well to small and mid-size enterprise operations. The Cloud Security Alliance has argued for a parallel shift toward Zero Standing Privileges (ZSP) in cloud-first PAM designs [5]. The architecture presented here is a companion pattern for organizations whose directory services and administrative estates remain predominantly on-premises. The following principles govern the design:

- Constrained delegation with time-bound elevation. No operator account holds persistent membership in Domain Admins, Enterprise Admins, Account Operators, or equivalent privileged groups for the purpose of day-to-day operations. All elevated access is Just-In-Time and expires automatically. The architecture retains delegated service identities (such as the gMSA-backed JEA caller) that hold standing technical privileges; these identities are constrained at the runtime layer to specific allowed operations and cannot be used interactively. Although break-glass accounts exist, they are only used in exceptional cases and are independently monitored.
- Constrained delegation at runtime boundary. The helpdesk-tier identity can only execute a fixed set of cmdlets enforced by the PowerShell language mode and the Just Enough Administration role capability. This is runtime enforcement and not a policy statement. The ability to invoke arbitrary code is not present.
- Blast-radius isolation. The internet-facing orchestration tier is physically separated from the execution tier. A compromise of the workflow engine does not yield direct access to the AD operations host or session gateway.
- Additive deployment. The architecture can be deployed alongside existing administrative practices. It does not require revoking existing Domain Admin memberships as a deployment prerequisite. Migration is explicit, per-person, and at the administrator's pace.
- Session recording as a deterrent control. Every interactive session through the gateway is recorded and retained. This is deterrent as much as it is investigative: administrators behave differently when they know the session is on the record.
- Approval as a human control and not a technical bypass. Approval workflows are routed through the organization's standard messaging platform so that the human element of the control is embedded in an interface that the approver already uses. A separate portal would result in lower compliance over time.
- Outrun-the-bear operational security. The architecture is not intended to be unbreachable. It aims to be substantially harder to attack than the next comparable target, using commodity components in a careful arrangement rather than exotic controls that require specialist operations.

4. Reference Architecture

The architecture is organized into three logical tiers deployed on dedicated compute instances under a type-1 hypervisor. The gateway and orchestration tiers can run on standalone Linux compute instances, including containers or virtual machines, depending on the resource and isolation requirements, whereas the execution tier is a hardened Windows host for directory operations. Operator-facing service paths are distinct from the dedicated management rail used to administer the underlying platform; that rail is reachable only from Secure Admin Workstations or Privileged Access Workstations.

4.1 Control Paths and Trust Boundaries

The operator-facing service surface was intentionally divided into two distinct paths. Interactive administration flows through the session gateway, which authenticates operators against the directory service over LDAPS, invokes an external MFA provider, and then brokers RDP, SSH, or VNC sessions to target systems. Workflow-based privileged changes flow through the cloud application proxy to the orchestration tier, where the cloud identity provider performs pre-authentication, and the messaging platform provides the approval step required before execution. Both paths ultimately rely on the same directory service as the identity and authorization anchor for the environment.

The Linux-based gateway and orchestration components are not domain-joined administrative hosts; they act as clients of the directory, cloud identity, and messaging services across the explicit network boundaries. Administrative access to the underlying virtualization platform, host operating systems, and container runtime is separated onto a dedicated management rail reachable only from Secure Admin Workstations or Privileged Access Workstations. That management rail is distinct from the operator-facing workflow and session-broker paths and is the only path by which the cluster and execution host are administered.

4.2 Tier Summary

Tier	Role	Exposure	Primary Controls
Session Gateway	Broker interactive RDP/SSH/VNC sessions	Internal network only	Directory-backed authentication over LDAPS; external MFA; session recording
Orchestration	Expose approval forms; translate requests	Internet via cloud application proxy	Cloud identity pre-authentication; approval workflow via messaging platform; reverse-proxy controls
Execution (JEA)	Execute directory changes via constrained runtime	Reachable only from orchestration + management rail	JEA role capability; constrained service identity; host EDR + IDS

5. Component Specifications

Component choices below are representative. Each can be substituted for a functional equivalent without changing the security posture of the architecture.

5.1 Session Gateway Tier

Role: The session gateway is the interactive administration front door. It accepts a browser connection, authenticates the operator against the directory service over LDAPS, invokes an external MFA provider as the second factor, and then brokers RDP, SSH, or VNC sessions to the target.

Representative implementation

Component	Representative choice	Substitutable with
Session broker	Apache Guacamole	Teleport, Boundary, commercial equivalents
Identity source	LDAPS against directory	SAML, OIDC, or direct IdP integration
MFA	External MFA provider via API	Any TOTP or push-based MFA integration
Session storage	Local filesystem with retention cron	Object storage with lifecycle policy
Database	Containerized PostgreSQL	Any supported relational database

Key security properties

- Gateway login and target system authentication are separate steps. After operator login, the broker connects to targets using either the operator's directory credentials or a connection-specific credential object, depending on connection policy.
- All sessions are recorded by default. A retention policy enforced by a scheduled cleanup ensures that recordings are neither retained indefinitely nor lost prematurely.
- The gateway is deployed behind a default-deny firewall. Only designated administrative network segments are permitted to reach the web interface.
- Container workloads run with no-new-privileges and all capabilities dropped, limiting the impact of a container escape.

5.2 Orchestration Tier

Role: The orchestration tier presents approval forms to operators, routes approval requests to the organization's messaging platform, and then translates approved operations into calls against the execution tier. It is internet-reachable via a pre-authenticated cloud application proxy server.

Representative implementation

Component	Representative choice	Substitutable with
Workflow engine	n8n (self-hosted)	Any workflow engine with HTTP endpoints
Reverse proxy	nginx with TLS termination	Caddy, HAProxy, Traefik
API bridge	Python/Flask on a systemd unit	Any language capable of HTTP + WinRM client
Remote execution client	pypsrp (Python PowerShell Remoting)	PSRP clients in Go, .NET, PowerShell
Internet exposure	Cloud application proxy with IdP pre-auth	Zero-trust network access provider, VPN-only
Messaging integration	Graph API to enterprise messaging platform	Slack, Mattermost, email-only approval

Allowed operations

Operations on privileged groups (Domain Admins, Enterprise Admins, Schema Admins, Account Operators, Server Operators, Backup Operators, Print Operators, DNS Admins, and equivalent built-in groups) are rejected at the API bridge before the request ever reaches the execution tier. This is defense in depth: the execution tier also blocks these groups at the JEA role-capability layer.

5.3 Execution Tier (JEA Host)

Role: The execution tier is the single host in the architecture that actually executes changes against Active Directory. Everything else routes requests here. It is treated as a sealed administrative appliance, reachable only from the orchestration tier and the hypervisor management rail, and accessed by administrators exclusively from Secure Admin Workstations (SAWs) or Privileged Access Workstations (PAWs). The constrained runtime used on this tier is Microsoft's Just Enough Administration (JEA), a PowerShell security feature that enforces role-based access control at the session layer [3].

Representative implementation

Component	Representative choice	Substitutable with
Operating system	Windows Server, current supported release	Any Windows Server release supporting JEA
Constrained runtime	PowerShell JEA role capability	No direct substitute on Windows; equivalent on Linux is RBAC + sudoers fine-grained policy
Identity	Group Managed Service Account (gMSA) [4]	Managed service identity with automatic password rotation
Remote protocol	WinRM HTTPS with certificate-based transport	PowerShell Remoting over SSH (modern releases)
Supporting tooling	Vendor-supplied AD management web UI	Any web-based AD management tool with HTTPS

Allowed cmdlets in the JEA endpoint

The JEA endpoint exposes eleven cmdlets. Every other cmdlet, every filesystem operation, and every form of arbitrary code execution is unavailable to any session connecting to this endpoint, regardless of the session's underlying identity.

Get-ADUser, Set-ADUser, Unlock-ADAccount, Enable-ADAccount, Disable-ADAccount, Set-ADAccountPassword, Get-ADGroupMember, Add-ADGroupMember, Remove-ADGroupMember, Get-ADGroup, Search-ADAccount

Delegation boundaries

- Allowed OUs: Standard user OU, standard security group OU.
- Denied OUs: Administrative accounts, IT operations accounts, service accounts, domain controllers.
- Blocked groups: Enforced at both the JEA layer and the orchestration tier API bridge. Privileged built-in groups are unreachable through this path.

6. Request Flows

6.1 Password Reset

1. Operator opens the password-reset form via the cloud application proxy URL.
2. The identity provider authenticates the operator with MFA.
3. The reverse proxy enforces any additional front-door authentication configured for the form path.
4. The operator enters the target username, the requester's identity, and a reason.
5. The workflow engine posts an approval request to the messaging platform with a resume link.
6. A second-person approver approves or denies the request in the messaging client.
7. If approved, the workflow engine calls the API bridge to generate a compliant passphrase.
8. The API bridge opens a WinRM session to the execution tier using the constrained service identity against the JEA endpoint.
9. JEA validates the cmdlet allow-list and executes the password change against the directory.
10. The workflow engine returns the new passphrase to the operator and logs the transaction to the SIEM.

6.2 Just-In-Time Privilege Elevation

1. Administrator opens the JIT form and selects the target username, the requested JIT group, the duration, and a justification.
2. The workflow engine posts an approval request to the messaging platform.
3. A designated approver reviews and approves or denies the request.
4. If approved, the API bridge calls JEA to execute Add-ADGroupMember.
5. The API bridge registers a scheduled removal for the approved duration.
6. On expiration, JEA executes Remove-ADGroupMember.
7. A Group Policy Restricted Groups baseline separately enforces intended memberships, providing independent reconciliation if scheduled removal fails.
8. All actions are logged to both the local audit trail and the SIEM.

7. Authentication and Identity

7.1 Session Gateway

Operator login to the session gateway is performed against the directory service over LDAPS using standard user identities. On successful bind, the gateway invokes an external MFA provider as the second factor. The local gateway database is not an independent identity source; it stores application state and can auto-provision user records after the first successful directory login.

7.2 Orchestration Tier

Operators reach the orchestration tier through a cloud application proxy that performs pre-authentication against the organization's cloud identity provider, with MFA enforced there rather than by the session gateway. The reverse proxy can apply an additional authentication layer for defense in depth. Approval is a separate control-plane dependency: the workflow engine posts to the messaging platform, an approver acts there, and the workflow resumes only after that response is returned.

7.3 Execution Tier

The orchestration tier reaches the execution tier through a constrained remoting path using a narrowly scoped service identity. The execution host performs the directory modifications, while the gateway and orchestration components remain non-domain-joined clients. Administrative access to the execution host and platform is limited to the PAW/SAW-only management rail.

8. Constrained Delegation Model

Constrained delegation in this architecture is enforced at three independent layers. An attacker who bypasses one still faces the others.

Layer	Mechanism	What it blocks
Orchestration	API bridge hardcoded group blocklist	Requests targeting privileged groups never reach the execution tier
Execution runtime	JEA role capability — allow-list of eleven cmdlets	Any cmdlet outside the allow-list; filesystem; arbitrary code
Directory	AD delegation + Group Policy Restricted Groups	Operations on denied OUs; stale privileged group memberships

9. Logging, Monitoring, and Audit

Every privileged action is recorded in at least two independent locations. This makes log tampering on any single host insufficient to hide an action.

- Session recordings from the session gateway, retained for 90 days with an enforced cleanup schedule.
- Workflow execution logs from the orchestration engine, including the identity of the requester, the identity of the approver, the parameters of the request, and the outcome.
- JEA transcripts on the execution tier, capturing every cmdlet invocation with input and output, stored locally and forwarded to the SIEM.
- JIT audit log with timestamps for both elevation and expiration events.
- Host-level telemetry from an endpoint detection and response agent on the execution tier, with behavioral detection and independent cloud log storage.
- IDS log analysis via a log-based IDS (e.g., CrowdSec) on the execution tier, providing behavioral detection independent of the EDR.
- Monitoring via an agent-based infrastructure monitoring system with alerting on service health and unusual state.

SIEM forwarding is configured for all tiers. The SIEM is the authoritative audit source; local logs are retained for investigative convenience but are not relied on for retention guarantees.

10. Design Trade-offs

No architecture is free of trade-offs. The following choices represent deliberate decisions rather than oversights. They are documented so that adopters can evaluate each against their own threat model.

10.1 Internal TLS with a self-signed private CA

Internal services use certificates issued by a self-signed private certificate authority. TLS verification is disabled at the workflow engine for outbound calls to internal services. The risk surface is limited to in-VLAN adversaries capable of traffic interception. This scenario can be mitigated by network segmentation and host-based IDS. External traffic is protected by CA-signed certificates at the edge proxy and the cloud application proxy.

Alternative for higher-threat environments: deploy an internal ACME-issuing certificate authority (e.g., step-ca, smallstep, or a Windows-integrated PKI) and re-enable strict TLS verification throughout.

10.2 Elevated API bridge on a management-isolated host

The API bridge on the orchestration tier runs with elevated privileges. This is deliberate: the orchestration components are administered only through a dedicated management rail reachable from Secure Admin Workstations or Privileged Access Workstations, and that management plane is distinct from the operator-facing workflow and session-broker paths. A compromise of the exposed service interfaces does not by itself grant administrative access to the underlying cluster, host operating systems, or execution tier. Within this access model, service-user isolation would reduce risk only incrementally relative to the operational complexity it introduces.

Alternative for environments where the orchestration tier is not a sealed appliance: run the bridge as a dedicated unprivileged user and use capabilities or systemd ambient capability grants for the specific operations that require them.

10.3 JIT expiration via in-process scheduler

Scheduled removal of JIT group memberships is handled in-process by the API bridge, with service-supervisor resilience (e.g., systemd with automatic restart) and audit alerting on anomalous group-membership durations. If the bridge service restarts during a JIT window, a pending removal may be lost, but the Group Policy Restricted Groups baseline provides independent reconciliation at the next policy refresh.

Alternative for environments without Group Policy reconciliation: persist scheduled removals to a durable backing store such as a database, cron, systemd timers, or an external job queue so restarts are non-destructive.

11. Cost Comparison vs. Commercial PAM

Commercial PAM pricing is highly product- and scope-dependent. Published vendor information shows both quote-based and published-list approaches [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. For example, ManageEngine PAM360 publishes annual subscription pricing starting at \$7,995 for 10 administrators and 25 keys, while vendors such as Delinea, BeyondTrust, and CyberArk direct prospective buyers to quote or demo workflows rather than a universal public list price. Broader IAM spend benchmarks exist [12], but they should not be interpreted as PAM-specific pricing. The table below therefore compares cost structures and documented pricing signals rather than asserting a single market-wide price.

When a commercial PAM is still the right call: environments with hundreds of administrators, audit requirements that mandate a named commercial product, a regulatory framework that effectively requires vendor support, or organizations without in-house expertise in directory delegation, PowerShell/JEA, Linux administration, and workflow tooling. The reference deployment figures in this paper reflect one environment and should not be treated as universal estimates. This architecture trades licensing cost for operational ownership, and that trade is only favorable when the team can absorb the ownership cost.

Capability	Commercial PAM (typical)	This architecture
Software licensing	Often quote-based; published examples start at \$7,995/year for 10 administrators and 25 keys	No software license fee for core components
Infrastructure	Vendor appliance, SaaS, or self-hosted platform	Three modest compute instances on existing virtualization platform
Initial deployment time	Environment-specific; may include procurement, integration, and professional services	Reference deployment: approximately 20 architect-hours in one environment
Ongoing maintenance	Vendor support contract plus administrator time	Reference deployment: approximately 2-4 administrator-hours per month
Session brokering + recording	Included	Included (open-source gateway)
JIT elevation	Included (varies by tier)	Included (JEA + GPO)
Approval workflows	Often included or module-dependent	Included (messaging platform)
Credential vaulting	Included	Not included -- use dedicated secret manager
Reporting and compliance	Polished, vendor-supported reporting and audit workflows	SIEM-based, administrator-built
Support model	Vendor support contract, often with optional professional services	Administrator ownership plus community support
Customization	Varies; often vendor-gated	Full source access
Vendor lock-in	Significant	None -- all components substitutable

12. Deployment Considerations

12.1 Prerequisites

- A virtualization platform with sufficient capacity for three modest compute instances (typical: 2-4 cores and 2-16 GB RAM each).
- An identity provider with MFA capability and application-proxy or reverse-proxy support.
- A messaging platform with an API suitable for bot posts and interactive replies.
- A directory service (Active Directory or equivalent) with the ability to delegate fine-grained permissions to an OU.
- A SIEM or centralized log aggregator with sufficient ingestion capacity.
- An endpoint detection and response agent for the execution tier.
- Group Policy or an equivalent configuration-enforcement mechanism.

12.2 Deployment Sequence

1. Build the execution tier first. Stand up the JEA host, configure the gMSA, define the role capability, and validate operations locally before any other component is connected to it.
2. Build the orchestration tier second. Deploy the workflow engine, API bridge, and reverse proxy. Validate the full request path from form submission to executed AD change, initially with an operator-initiated approval to a test account.
3. Integrate the messaging platform. Add approval routing and verify that denied requests stop the workflow as expected.
4. Integrate the cloud application proxy. Validate that external access requires IdP pre-authentication.
5. Build the session gateway tier. Configure LDAPS, MFA, and session recording. Enable recording on every connection at creation time, not after the fact.
6. Enable logging and monitoring. Forward all relevant logs to the SIEM. Deploy the EDR and IDS agents on the execution tier. Verify alerts fire on representative test events.
7. Enforce the Group Policy baseline. Deploy Restricted Groups policies to enforce the intended membership of privileged groups, and deploy JIT-group-to-local-admin mappings on target systems.
8. Migrate administrators incrementally. Remove standing privileged group memberships one administrator at a time, only after each has validated JIT elevation works for their workflow.

13. Conclusion

A defensible privileged access management posture does not require a commercial product. It requires a clear threat model, deliberate separation between orchestration and execution, constrained delegation enforced at the runtime boundary, second-person approval embedded in the tools operators already use, and an audit record that survives tampering on any single host.

The reference deployment described here was built for an organization with several hundred users and replaced an existing commercial PAM product. The value is not in any one software package. It is in the control boundaries: session brokering separated from privileged execution, directory operations constrained at the execution tier, and every privileged action tied to a human-attributable approval and audit trail before it runs.

Administrators adapting this pattern to their own environment should begin with the threat model and operating constraints. The components are the easy part. The hard part is the discipline required to keep the controls intact: recording every session, requiring a second person for elevated actions, forwarding logs to an independent destination, and reducing standing privilege at a pace the organization can actually sustain.

Appendix A: Component Inventory

The following inventory lists the functional roles in the architecture. Specific software packages are examples only; any functional equivalent can be substituted.

Tier	Component Role	Example Software
Session Gateway	Browser-based session broker	Apache Guacamole
Session Gateway	Session database	PostgreSQL
Session Gateway	MFA integration	External MFA provider API
Orchestration	Workflow engine	n8n
Orchestration	Reverse proxy with TLS	nginx
Orchestration	API bridge to execution tier	Python/Flask
Orchestration	Remote execution client	pypsrp
Orchestration	External exposure	Cloud application proxy
Execution	Windows Server OS	Current supported release
Execution	Constrained runtime	PowerShell JEA
Execution	Identity	gMSA
Execution	AD management UI (optional)	Vendor-supplied web tool
Cross-tier	SIEM	Organization-standard SIEM
Cross-tier	EDR	Organization-standard EDR
Cross-tier	IDS (log-based)	CrowdSec or equivalent
Cross-tier	Infrastructure monitoring	Nagios or equivalent
Cross-tier	Directory service	Active Directory
Cross-tier	Identity provider	Organization IdP with MFA
Cross-tier	Messaging platform	Organization messaging platform

Appendix B: References

References were reviewed against primary vendor or standards sources where available. All URLs were accessed and verified in April 2026.

- [1] S. Rose, O. Borchert, S. Mitchell, and S. Connelly, Zero Trust Architecture, NIST Special Publication 800-207, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, Aug. 2020. doi: 10.6028/NIST.SP.800-207. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-207>
- [2] Microsoft, "Securing privileged access Enterprise access model," Microsoft Learn, 2024. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/security/privileged-access-workstations/privileged-access-access-model>
- [3] Microsoft, "Overview of Just Enough Administration (JEA)," Microsoft Learn, PowerShell documentation, 2024. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/powershell/scripting/security/remoting/jea/overview>
- [4] Microsoft, "Group Managed Service Accounts overview," Microsoft Learn, Windows Server Identity documentation, 2024. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows-server/identity/ad-ds/manage/group-managed-service-accounts/group-managed-service-accounts/group-managed-service-accounts-overview>
- [5] Cloud Security Alliance, Managing Privileged Access in a Cloud-First World, CSA Research Publication, 2025. <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/artifacts/managing-privileged-access-in-a-cloud-first-world>
- [6] Microsoft, "Enhanced Security Admin Environment (ESAE) architecture mainstream retirement," Microsoft Learn, Privileged Access documentation, 2024. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/security/privileged-access-workstations/esae-retirement>
- [7] ManageEngine, "PAM360 Pricing & Plans," ManageEngine, 2026. <https://www.manageengine.com/privileged-access-management/pricing.html>
- [8] ManageEngine, "How much does a PAM implementation really cost?," ManageEngine, 2026. <https://www.manageengine.com/privileged-access-management/pam-implementation-cost.html>
- [9] Delinea, "Request a Quote," Delinea, 2026. <https://delinea.com/request-a-quote>
- [10] BeyondTrust, "Password Safe Pricing," BeyondTrust, 2026. <https://www.beyondtrust.com/products/password-safe/pricing>
- [11] CyberArk, "Privileged Access Manager demo request," CyberArk, 2026. <https://www.cyberark.com/try-buy/privileged-access-manager-demo/>
- [12] APQC, "Percentage of total cybersecurity spend allocated to identity and access management (IAM)," APQC, 2026. <https://www.apqc.org/resources/benchmarking/open-standards-benchmarking/measures/percentage-total-cybersecurity-spend-7>

Appendix C: Glossary

EDR. Endpoint Detection and Response. Host-based security software with behavioral detection and remote investigation capabilities.

gMSA. Group Managed Service Account. A domain-managed identity with automatic password rotation; the password is never materialized outside the domain.

IDS. Intrusion Detection System. In this architecture, a log-based IDS providing behavioral detection independent of the EDR.

IdP. Identity Provider. The organization's authoritative source of authentication and MFA.

JEA. Just Enough Administration. A PowerShell feature that constrains a session to a specific allow-list of cmdlets and parameters, enforced at the runtime layer.

JIT. Just-In-Time (privilege elevation). Time-bounded group membership granted on demand and automatically revoked on expiration.

LDAPS. LDAP over TLS. The encrypted form of the directory access protocol.

MFA. Multi-factor authentication.

PAM. Privileged Access Management.

PAW. Privileged Access Workstation. A hardened workstation used exclusively for administrative tasks, with no general-purpose software or internet access.

PSRP. PowerShell Remoting Protocol. The protocol used to execute PowerShell sessions on remote hosts.

SAW. Secure Admin Workstation. Synonym for PAW in some organizations.

SIEM. Security Information and Event Management. The centralized log aggregation and correlation system.

WinRM. Windows Remote Management. The transport mechanism for PowerShell Remoting.

Disclaimer: This document presents a reference architecture informed by one production deployment, not a universal implementation standard. Adopters should evaluate it against their own threat model, regulatory requirements, operational maturity, and risk tolerance before production use.